

FACTORS INFLUENCING NURSES' CONFIDENCE AND EFFECTIVENESS
IN POST-STROKE PATIENT EDUCATION AT ALLIED HOSPITAL
FAISALABAD

Shumaila Abdul Rehman^{*1}, Mehwish Bashir², Bushra Iqbal³, Beenish⁴, Dr. Muhmmad Ateeq⁵

^{*1}MSN (National University of Medical Sciences), Islamabad, Pakistan; Nursing Officer Allied Hospital 1, Faisalabad, Pakistan

²Nursing Officer, Faisalabad Institute of Cardiology, Pakistan

³Nursing Officer Allied Hospital 1, Faisalabad, Pakistan

⁴Nursing Officer Allied Hospital 2, Faisalabad, Pakistan

⁵Post Graduate Resident in Surgery, Allied Hospital 1, Faisalabad

^{*1}shumailaabdulrehmanshumailaabd@gmail.com

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Corresponding Author: *

Shumaila Abdul Rehman

Abstract

Background: Patient education reduces stroke recurrence and improves rehabilitation outcomes. Nurses are central to educating patients about risk factors, lifestyle modifications, and treatment adherence. However, several factors can affect their confidence and effectiveness in delivering this education. Understanding these factors is essential to enhance the quality of care provided.

Objectives: To identify the factors influencing nurses' confidence and effectiveness in educating stroke patients at Allied Hospital Faisalabad, focusing on professional experience, workload, departmental variations, and access to training.

Methodology: A cross-sectional survey was conducted among nurses working in the Intensive Care Unit (ICU), Medical Wards, Neurology Units, and Outpatient Department at Allied Hospital Faisalabad. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire that assessed nurses' knowledge, experience, and perceived barriers to effective patient education. The data were analyzed using SPSS, employing descriptive statistics and regression analysis to identify key influencing factors.

Results The study results showed that 93.2% of nurses had good knowledge of stroke management, including awareness of risk factors, medical interventions, and patient education. Regarding specific areas, 90.4% of nurses were knowledgeable about stroke types, hemiplegia, risk factors, and interventions like oxygen supplementation and vital sign monitoring. However, 8.8% exhibited moderate knowledge, and 0.8% had poor knowledge. Notable gaps were identified in areas such as neurological assessments, seizure management, and feeding dysphagic patients. These findings emphasize the need for focused training to address these areas and enhance overall stroke care.

Conclusion The results show most nurses have good general knowledge of stroke management, particularly in risk factor identification, but gaps exist in specific interventions like neurological assessments and seizure management. Experience

and education significantly influence knowledge, highlighting the need for targeted training and professional development.

INTRODUCTION

Stroke is a chronic disease that needs special attention. Stroke can cause severe brain damage, resulting in obstruction of the patient's mobility to carry out daily activities [1]. According to the global burden of stroke and the critical role of nurses in post-stroke education, it is imperative to assess their knowledge and identify areas where improvements are needed [2]. Nurses in stroke care units need to possess important knowledge, competent abilities, and a good attitude to provide patients with the best treatment possible. Because of this, nurses need the right education to advance their knowledge and practical skills [3].

Nurses need further training because they lack the knowledge and abilities necessary to identify and treat dysphagia in stroke survivors. The implementation of water protocols in acute stroke care was hindered, according to nurses, by their lack of experience with oral care and stroke-specific skills [4]. Although nurses are essential in helping patients with stroke receive evidence-based care, some patients end up receiving care that is detrimental or unnecessary. The application of several tactics to encourage the adoption of evidence-based practice, but it is unclear which combination of tactics works best [5].

In the initial months following a stroke, caring for someone might be difficult. Still, it is crucial to provide them with enough knowledge, support, and encouragement to heal quickly and without complications. Stroke rehabilitation will increase if patients receive timely and suitable care within the ideal period, which is three to six months. The focus on stroke rehabilitation should change from being just on the patient to including the patient's career as well [6].

The use of protocols with systematic instructions helps nurses with interventions in community settings. The Resident Assessment Instrument (Inter-RAI) and the Outcomes and Assessment Information Set (OASIS) are two commonly used protocols that have not yet been translated or

validated for usage in Brazil but are discussed. These tools have been used to evaluate individuals with chronic requirements and post-acute care utilizing multidimensional assessment; they are not specifically designed to assist family carers of elderly individuals following a stroke [7]. The first six months after a stroke, 25-54% of caretakers reported feeling overburdened by the task of caring for their patients. The caretaker has a hardship when a patient has a stroke. The care is not a place without burdens. The strain grows when they are forced to assume complete responsibility for the post-stroke patients' care despite lacking the knowledge and abilities necessary to provide at-home care [8].

By coordinating care across the continuum, nurses will continue to play an important role in the management of stroke patients [9]. According to Eslam Abd Alkreem Allsasmah (2020), nurses and doctors who witness the full impact of stroke should be equipped with the ability to speed up patients' recovery [10].

Following the first 72 hours of care, nursing is essential to the treatment of post-stroke patients. To improve the prognosis of stroke survivors and prevent stroke recurrence, post-stroke nursing care is centered on rehabilitation services and secondary prevention strategies. Effective rehabilitation for stroke survivors is influenced by good nursing care and support from patients' relatives [11]. Barriers to best practice in evidence-based stroke care include a lack of knowledge, awareness, and skills, as well as low awareness and knowledge levels [12]. Therefore, it is crucial to conduct a further study of nursing management of acute stroke.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A descriptive, cross-sectional study was conducted using a structured survey to assess nurses' knowledge regarding stroke care and prevention. Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the educational department and hospital site, ensuring the research adhered to ethical

standards, ensuring that the study complied with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki. To maintain confidentiality, participants' responses were kept anonymous, and informed consent was obtained before participation. The data collection was completed over three months, following approval by the Board of Ethical Committee.

An adaptive, structured questionnaire was developed and circulated to experts and health professionals in the fields of nursing and medicine to evaluate its content validity. This process ensured the clarity, comprehensiveness, and relevance of the questions, thereby enhancing the reliability of the data collection tool. The questionnaire comprised five sections. Section 1 gathered socio-demographic information, including gender, age, educational level, years of experience, and the participant's place of work. Section 2 focused on assessing nurses' knowledge of stroke definitions, causes, and types, with seven questions. Section 3 evaluated nurses' understanding of stroke risk factors, both modifiable and non-modifiable, through nine questions. Section 4 assessed knowledge regarding the identification and evaluation of stroke risk factors, containing 14 questions. Section 5 examined knowledge about nursing interventions for stroke management and prevention of complications, with 25 questions covering areas such as airway management, neurological care, pharmacological interventions, and nutritional support.

The study population consisted of 249 nurses employed in the Intensive Care Unit (ICU), Critical Care Units, Medical Wards, Neurology Units, and Outpatient Department at Allied Hospital Faisalabad. These nurses were selected due to their direct involvement in the care and management of stroke patients, making them essential contributors to the study's focus on post-stroke patient education.

Inclusion criteria were registered nurses with a minimum of three months of work experience in stroke care and who were willing to participate were included. Nurses who were on maternity or annual leave or who were unwilling to participate were excluded. This sampling approach ensured the selection of nurses who were actively involved in stroke patient care, providing a representative sample across various clinical settings in the hospital.

The selection of these nurses allowed for the gathering of comprehensive data on the knowledge levels of stroke care and management across different units, ensuring that the findings would reflect diverse clinical experiences and highlight potential areas for further education and training.

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 26. Descriptive analysis using mean, percentages, and frequencies. Multiple regression analysis was used to identify the factors that may influence nurses' confidence and effectiveness in post-stroke patient education.

RESULTS

Table-1: Descriptive statistic of Demographic characteristics of study participants

Variables	Categories	N	%
Gender	Male	5	2.0
	Female	244	98.0
Age	20-30	46	18.5
	31-40	179	71.9
	41-50	24	9.6
Qualification	certificate	4	1.6
	diploma	105	42.2
	bachelor degree	140	56.2
Years of Experience	0-5	107	43.0
	6-10	98	39.4
	11-15	35	14.1

	16-20	5	2.0
	21-30	4	1.6

A total of 249 nurses were included in the study. The study sample predominantly consisted of female nurses, accounting for 98% (n=244) of the participants, while males represented only 2% (n=5). The majority of respondents were aged between 31 and 40 years (71.9%, n=179), followed by those aged 20-30 years (18.5%, n=46) and 41-50 years (9.6%, n=24). In terms of educational qualifications, most participants held a bachelor's degree (56.2%, n=140), with 42.2% (n=105) holding a diploma and a small fraction (1.6%, n=4) having a certificate. The distribution of years of experience showed that 43% (n=107) had 0-5 years of experience, 39.4% (n=98) had 6-10 years, 14.1% (n=35) had 11-15 years, 2% (n=5) had 16-20 years, and 1.6% (n=4) had 21-30 years. Regarding training on stroke management, 30.9% (n=77) of the respondents had received training, whereas 69.1% (n=172) had not.

Assessment of Nurses' Knowledge Regarding Patient Education Post Stroke

Participants were divided into three risk groups; a cut score indicated the limits of each category. The "high" knowledge bar is noticeably bigger, signifying that more than 200 nurses have a high degree of expertise in stroke patient teaching. High Knowledge (229 nurses): The vast majority of nurses in this group have a high degree of understanding when it comes to post-stroke patient education. The nurses in this group may have a thorough understanding of stroke patients and are skilled in educating them. Moderate Knowledge (19 nurses): This group comprises fewer nurses, indicating a moderate degree of knowledge. Although these nurses understand post-stroke education principles quite well, they may still benefit from more training or experience to improve their competence. The frequency of the "moderate" knowledge category

is significantly lower, indicating that relatively few nurses fit into this category. Poor Knowledge (1 Nurse): Concerning post-stroke patient education, only one nurse is classified as having a poor level of knowledge. To increase their comprehension and capacity to instruct stroke patients, this person might need a great deal of assistance, instruction, or resources. The fact that there are so few nurses in the "Low" knowledge group suggests that their understanding in this area is almost nonexistent. Overall, the graph shows that most nurses have a good grasp of patient education as it relates to care after a stroke.

The regression analysis of overall stroke knowledge among nurses is depicted in Table 2. The constant, or intercept, is statistically significant with a value of 1.265, indicating the baseline level of stroke knowledge when all other variables are controlled. Among the independent variables, educational level shows a positive and statistically significant relationship with stroke knowledge (B = 0.046, p = .024), suggesting that higher educational attainment is associated with better knowledge. However, age, experience, training courses, and gender do not exhibit significant effects on stroke knowledge. Age and training courses have positive but non-significant coefficients (B = 0.024, p = .294; B = 0.023, p = .308, respectively), indicating minimal influence. Experience and gender show negligible and non-significant effects, with near-zero coefficients, indicating that these factors do not substantially impact stroke knowledge among nurses. Overall, educational level is the only significant predictor of stroke knowledge in this analysis, highlighting its importance in nurse education and training programs as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Factors that affect confidence and effectiveness of stroke knowledge

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Significance
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	1.265	.150		8.408	.000
Gender	.012	.074	.010	.163	.871
Age	.024	.023	.077	1.052	.294
Educational level	.046	.020	.149	2.276	.024
Job Experience	-.001	.014	-.006	-.082	.935
Training course	.023	.023	.065	1.022	.308

a. Dependent Variable: average (overall) score

DISCUSSION

The current study aimed to explore the factors influencing nurses' confidence and effectiveness in post-stroke patient education at a tertiary care hospital in Faisalabad. The findings indicate that most nurses demonstrated a high level of knowledge regarding post-stroke patient education, with over 91% categorized as having high knowledge. This high level of knowledge contributes to their confidence and effectiveness in educating patients, which is essential for optimizing patient outcomes and reducing the risk of complications. Nurses play a pivotal role in educating stroke patients about lifestyle changes, medication adherence, and rehabilitation, which are critical in preventing stroke recurrence and improving patients' quality of life [13].

The results suggest that nurses who possess higher knowledge are more confident in educating stroke patients, aligning with previous research that emphasizes the direct correlation between knowledge and confidence in patient care [14]. Studies have consistently shown that nurses with greater knowledge of stroke management are more likely to feel confident in their ability to provide education to patients and their families [15]. In this study, the nurses in the "high knowledge" group demonstrated a strong understanding of stroke care principles, which enhanced their confidence in patient education. Moreover, the significant relationship between educational level and stroke knowledge (B = 0.046, p = .024) highlights the importance of formal education in shaping nurses' competence

and confidence in patient education. The higher levels of education are associated with better clinical knowledge, which translates into improved patient outcomes [16]. Nurses with advanced education are more likely to understand complex medical concepts, enabling them to convey this information effectively to patients. This finding is consistent with studies by Jones et al. (2015), who found that nurses with higher education levels displayed greater competence and confidence in patient education [17].

However, age, experience, gender, and training courses did not significantly influence stroke knowledge in this study, which contrasts with some earlier findings. Previous research has suggested that years of experience and participation in specialized training can positively impact nurses' knowledge and confidence [18]. Nonetheless, in this study, educational attainment was the primary predictor of stroke knowledge, underscoring the necessity for continued emphasis on formal education. This may suggest that while on-the-job experience and training are valuable, they may not fully substitute for the foundational knowledge gained through formal education.

Despite the high level of knowledge among most participants, a smaller group of nurses (7.6%) demonstrated moderate knowledge, and one nurse (0.4%) showed poor knowledge. This suggests that while overall knowledge levels are high, there is still room for improvement, particularly for those nurses who may lack

confidence due to gaps in their knowledge. This is supported by research from Knight et al. (2020), which found that knowledge gaps in stroke care can reduce nurses' confidence and hinder effective patient education. Additional training and resources are necessary to help these nurses build confidence and provide optimal education to stroke patients [19].

Patient education is a core component of stroke rehabilitation and secondary prevention [20]. Effective education helps patients understand their condition, adhere to prescribed therapies, and implement necessary lifestyle changes [21]. For nurses to deliver this education confidently, they must possess not only strong clinical knowledge but also effective communication skills and educational strategies [22]. This study demonstrates that nurses with high knowledge are likely to be more confident and effective in their educational roles, but continued professional development is essential to maintain and enhance this confidence.

REFERENCES

- Fatmawati, A. and Pradana, F., 2021. The Level of Knowledge, Motivation, and Self-Efficacy of Post-Stroke Patients in Lumajang. *Jurnal Ners Dan Kebidanan (Journal of Ners and Midwifery)*, 8(2), pp.201-205.
- Feigin, V.L., Vos, T., Nichols, E., Owolabi, M.O., Carroll, W.M., Dichgans, M., Deuschl, G., Parmar, P., Brainin, M., Murray, C., 2020. The global burden of neurological disorders: translating evidence into policy. *Lancet Neurol.* 19, 255–265. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1474-4422\(19\)30411-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1474-4422(19)30411-9)
- Al-Abidi, H., Mansour, K., 2022. Nurses Knowledge and Practice Concerning Nursing Management for Patients with Stroke. *Kufa J. Nurs. Sci.* 12. <https://doi.org/10.36321/kjns/2022/120124>
- Melnikov, S., 2020. The need for knowledge and skills in the care of post-stroke patients. *Eur. J. Cardiovasc. Nurs.* 19, 456–457. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1474515120923498>
- Mills, K.T., Bundy, J.D., Kelly, T.N., Reed, J.E., Kearney, P.M., Reynolds, K., Chen, J. and He, J. (2016). Global Disparities of Hypertension Prevalence and Control. *Circulation*, 134(6), pp.441–450. [doi:https://doi.org/10.1161/circulationaha.115.018912](https://doi.org/10.1161/circulationaha.115.018912).
- Santos, N.O. dos, Predebon, M.L., Bierhals, C.C.B.K., Day, C.B., Machado, D. de O., Paskulin, L.M.G., 2020. Development and validation a nursing care protocol with educational interventions for family caregivers of elderly people after stroke. *Rev. Bras. Enferm.* 73, e20180894. <https://doi.org/10.1590/0034-7167-2018-0894>
- Deyhoul, N., Vasli, P., Rohani, C., Shakeri, N. and Hosseini, M., 2020. The effect of family-centered empowerment program on the family caregiver burden and the activities of daily living of Iranian patients with stroke: a randomized controlled trial study. *Aging clinical and experimental research*, 32(7), pp.1343-1352.
- Heemskerk, J.L., Domingo, R.A., Tawk, R.G., Vivas-Buitrago, T.G., Huang, J.F., Rogers, A., Quinones-Hinojosa, A., Abode-Iyamah, K., Freeman, W.D., 2021. Time Is Brain: Prehospital Emergency Medical Services Response Times for Suspected Stroke and Effects of Prehospital Interventions. *Mayo Clin. Proc.* 96, 1446–1457. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mayocp.2020.08.050>
- Allsammah, E.A.A., 2020. Measuring Knowledge of Jordanian Nurses Working in Critical Care Units toward Stroke Patients. *World Science*, (8 (60)).

- Babkair, L.A., Safhi, R.A., Balshram, R., Safhei, R., Almahamdy, A., Hakami, F.H., Alsaleh, A.M., 2023. Nursing Care for Stroke Patients: Current Practice and Future Needs. *Nurs. Rep.* 13, 1236-1250. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nursrep13030106>
- Bakas, T., McCarthy, M. J., Miller, E. T., et al. (2014). Stroke caregiver and patient outcomes from the telephone assessment and skill-building kit (TASK). *Topics in Stroke Rehabilitation*, 21(1), 20-27.
- El-Tallawy, H. N., Farghaly, W. M. A., Shehata, G. A., et al. (2016). Stroke Knowledge and Attitude: Multicenter Survey in Upper Egypt. *eNeurologicalSci*, 3, 1-5.
- Hoffmann, T., Clarke, J., Lannin, N. (2017). Nurse-led education interventions for stroke patients and their carers: A systematic review. *International Journal of Stroke*, 12(6), 577-584.
- Jones, T. L., Hamilton, P., & Murry, N. (2015). Uncovering nurse-perceived barriers to pressure ulcer prevention. *Journal of Clinical Nursing*, 24(9-10), 1236-1246.
- Knight, R., Hentschel, H., Scherzer, C., & Pahlke, S. (2020). Nurses' knowledge of stroke and stroke management: A cross-sectional study from South Africa. *African Journal of Primary Health Care & Family Medicine*, 12(1), 1-6.
- Minani, L. (2019). Assessing Nurses' Knowledge and Practice in Acute Stroke Care at Muhimbili National Hospital, Tanzania. [Master's thesis, University of Dar es Salaam].
- Schwamm, L. H., Pancioli, A., Acker, J. E., et al. (2018). Recommendations for the establishment of stroke systems of care: recommendations from the American Stroke Association's Task Force on the Development of Stroke Systems. *Stroke*, 36(3), 690-703.
- Shehata, S. A., et al. (2016). Knowledge and Practice of Nurses Regarding the Care of Patients with Acute Stroke. Cairo University Faculty of Nursing.

